

Phosphorylation and thiophosphorylation of 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole and their biological activities

Chandni Jain, Ram Gopal, Lalita Panwar and Meena Nagar*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : nagar_meena@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Some novel organophosphorus compounds of the type $[(C_{14}H_{11}N_2S)_nP(O)Cl_{3-n}]/[(C_{14}H_{11}N_2S)_nP(S)Cl_{3-n}]$ {where $n=1-3$ } have been easily synthesized by the reaction of 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole ($C_{14}H_{11}N_2S$) with phosphorus oxychloride ($POCl_3$)/phosphorus thiochloride ($PSCl_3$) and triethylamine in 1 : 1 : 1, 2 : 1 : 2 and 3 : 1 : 3 molar ratio in anhydrous THF/ CH_2Cl_2 . All these viscous organophosphates have been characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight measurements and FT-IR, NMR (1H and ^{31}P) spectral studies. The antibacterial activity of these organophosphate derivatives has been evaluated against pathogenic bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (+ve) and *Escherichia coli* (-ve). The antifungal activity of these organophosphates has been evaluated against pathogenic fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum*. These organophosphates were also found to be insecticidal when tested against *Periplaneta americana*. The results indicate that organophosphate derivatives are found more active than the parent compound.

Keywords : 2-(4'-Aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole, phosphorus oxychloride, phosphorus thiochloride, antibacterial activity, antifungal activity.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compound analogues and their derivatives have attracted strong interest in medicinal chemistry due to their biological and pharmacological properties. A number of heterocyclic derivatives containing nitrogen and sulfur atom serve as a unique and versatile scaffolds for experimental drug design. Benzothiazole is one of the most important heterocycles that has received overwhelming response owing to its diversified molecular design and remarkable optical, liquid and electronic properties^{1,2}. Benzothiazole derivatives possesses a wide spectrum of biological applications such as antitumor³⁻⁵, antimicrobial⁶⁻⁹, antiinflammatory^{10,11}, anticonvulsants^{12,13}, antidiabetic^{14,15}, and diuretic¹⁶ etc.

Organophosphorus compounds containing heterocyclic moiety increase the protonation at the site of pesticides and enhance their biological activity. Various phosphorylated compounds of benzothiazole and amines are also associated with antifungal activities¹⁷. In continuation of our work on organophosphates¹⁸⁻²¹, herein we report the synthesis of biologically active organophosphate derived from 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole.

Results and discussion

The reactions of phosphorus oxychloride ($POCl_3$)/phosphorus thiochloride ($PSCl_3$) with 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 in the presence of stoichiometric amounts of triethylamine in dry tetrahydrofuran (THF)/ CH_2Cl_2 yielded the phosphorylated and thiophosphorylated benzothiazole derivatives (**1-6**) (Scheme 1). These reactions are quite facile and quantitative. All these derivatives are viscous solids, hygroscopic in nature and are soluble in dimethyl formamide, dimethyl sulphoxide, chloroform etc. The molecular weight measurements indicate their monomeric nature in refluxing anhydrous benzene.

IR spectra :

The assignments of some important bands are summarized in Table 1. In the 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole ligand, an absorption band is found at 3400–3300 cm^{-1} , which is characteristics of the $-NH_2$ group. Bands due to $\nu(NH_2)$ at 3400–3300 cm^{-1} were absent in all reported phosphorylated and thiophosphorylated benzothiazole derivatives due to the removal of proton from 2-substituted $-NH_2$ group during the phosphoryla-

where $n = 1, 2, 3$ and $X = \text{O/S}$

Scheme 1. Schematic presentation of organophosphate derivatives (**1-6**).

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of organophosphate derivatives (**1-6**)

Compound	$\nu(\text{P-N-C})$	$\nu(\text{P-NH})$	$\nu(\text{P=O})$	$\nu(\text{P-S})$	$\nu(\text{P-Cl})$
1 $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S})\text{P}(\text{O})\text{Cl}_2$	1035	2940	1230	–	515 (sym)
	650	2850			605 (asym)
2 $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S})\text{P}(\text{S})\text{Cl}_2$	1045	2950	–	820 (I)	520 (sym)
	650	2855		655 (II)	610 (asym)
3 $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S})_2\text{P}(\text{O})\text{Cl}$	1040	2945	1245	–	520 (sym)
	650	2860			600 (asym)
4 $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S})_2\text{P}(\text{S})\text{Cl}$	1050	2960	–	850 (I)	525 (sym)
	655	2870		695 (II)	620 (asym)
5 $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S})_3\text{P}(\text{O})$	1055	2955	1255	–	–
	650	2855			
6 $(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S})_3\text{P}(\text{S})$	1060	2965	–	950 (I)	–
	660	2890		720 (II)	

tion reaction. These gets supported by the appearance of new absorption band at $2965\text{--}2940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ along with $2890\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for N-H stretching of P-NH band. In phosphorylated and thiophosphorylated derivatives of 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole, characteristic stretching vibrations $\nu(\text{P=S})$, $\nu(\text{P=O})$ and $\nu(\text{P-N-C})$ appears at $900\text{--}820\text{ cm}^{-1}$ along with $720\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1255\text{--}1230\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1060\text{--}1035\text{ cm}^{-1}$ along with $660\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

^1H NMR and ^{31}P NMR spectra :

All the characteristic data of NMR (^1H and ^{31}P) of phosphorylated and thiophosphorylated derivatives are summarized in Table 2. In the ^1H NMR spectra of phosphory-

lated and thiophosphorylated derivatives the -NH proton signal was observed at δ 6.2–5.4 ppm as doublet due to 'P' splitting. Aromatic protons were observed at δ 6.5–8.5 ppm. ^{31}P NMR spectrum of all the phosphorylated and thiophosphorylated benzothiazole derivatives exhibits only one resonance signal at δ 58–74 ppm indicating tetra coordination around the phosphorus atom.

Antibacterial activity :

The results of the antibacterial activity of organophosphate derivatives (**1-6**) have been compared with standard Streptomycin and are summarized in Table 3. The organisms selected for the studies are *Staphylococcus aureus* (+ve) and *Escherichia coli* (–ve). The antibacterial acti-

Table 2. ^1H NMR and ^{31}P NMR spectral data (δ , ppm) of organophosphate derivatives (1-6)

Compound	^1H NMR (δ , ppm)		^{31}P NMR
	P-NH	Aromatic proton	
1 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(O)Cl ₂	5.5	6.5–7.5	68.5
2 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(S)Cl ₂	5.7	7.7–8.4	70.1
3 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(O)Cl	5.7	7.9–8.5	62.7
4 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(S)Cl	5.8	7.5–8.1	65.8
5 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(O)	5.8	7.8–8.4	59.5
6 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(S)	5.6	7.8–8.2	64.9

Table 3. Antibacterial screening data of organophosphate derivatives (1-6)

Diameter of inhibition zone after 24 h (conc. in ppm)

Compound	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>		<i>Escherichia coli</i>	
	500	1000	500	1000
1 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(O)Cl ₂	22	34	24	36
2 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(S)Cl ₂	25	36	27	38
3 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(O)Cl	26	37	21	39
4 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(S)Cl	28	38	25	45
5 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(O)	30	40	33	45
6 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(S)	32	43	42	51
Streptomycin (standard)	45	60	52	64

Antifungal activity was evaluated by a paper disk plate method. The comparative results of antibacterial activity are shown in graph (Fig. 1), indicate that these organophosphate derivatives are less toxic than standard Streptomycin and their antibacterial activity increases with the increase in the concentration.

Fig. 1. Bar graph showing the relative antifungal activity of compounds (1-6).

Antifungal activity :

All the results of antifungal activity of organophosphate derivatives are shown in Table 4 and Fig. 2. The

organophosphate derivatives have been screened for fungicidal properties against *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* at concentration of 50, 100 and 200 ppm. The radial growth method was used to check an activity against fungi by taking Dithane M-45 as a standard. The inference drawn from the table reveals that the activity of organophosphate derivatives increases with an increase in concentration. Derivatives having a P=S bond resulted in higher toxicity than derivatives having P=O bond. Although the toxicity of all the newly synthesized derivatives was quite high, it was less than the standard Dithane M-45.

Insecticidal activity :

The comparative results of insecticidal activity are shown in Table 5 and Fig. 3. The results of the insecticidal activity of organophosphates (1-6) have been compared with conventional insecticide Malathion, taken as standard. All the results reveal that these organophosphates are less toxic than the standard Malathion and their insecticidal activity increases with the increase in concentration. Organophosphates having P=S bond resulted in higher toxicity than having P=O bond with the same substituents attached to the phosphorus.

Experimental

All manipulations for the synthesis and characterization of complexes were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions. Solvents were dried by conventional methods and distilled prior to use. Melting points were determined by the capillary method and are uncorrected. All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Phosphorus oxychloride (POCl₃)/Phosphorus thiochloride (PSCl₃) and 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole were purchased from Fluka and Sigma Aldrich respectively. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded as KBr disks on a SHIMADZU 8400 S FT-IR spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL AL 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal reference. The ^{31}P NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL AL 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer at 121.49 MHz in CDCl₃ using TMS and 85% H₃PO₄ as internal and external reference respectively. Nitrogen was estimated by the Messenger's method. Chlorine was estimated volumetrically by the Volhard method. Phosphorus was estimated as ammonium phosphomolybdate. The molecular weights were determined by the Rast Camphor method.

Table 4. Antifungal screening data of organophosphate derivatives (1-6)

Compound	Average % inhibition after 72 h (conc. in ppm)					
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>			<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>		
	50	100	200	50	100	200
1 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(O)Cl ₂	40.5	50.2	65.3	38.7	48.0	65.7
2 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(S)Cl ₂	59.0	61.5	78.4	62.3	67.5	76.6
3 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(O)Cl	61.5	62.7	75.5	68.1	71.3	78.6
4 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(S)Cl	64.2	68.4	81.3	70.8	74.7	82.3
5 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(O)	65.4	69.4	85.3	73.5	80.1	95.2
6 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(S)	70.2	80.2	89.7	75.8	85.4	98.5
Dithane M-45 (standard)	77	94	100	75	95	100

Fig. 2. Bar graph showing the relative antibacterial activity of compounds (1-6).

Fig. 3. Bar graph showing the relative insecticidal activity of compounds (1-6).

Table 5. Insecticidal evaluation data of organophosphate derivatives (1-6)

Compound	Concentration (µg/cm ²)	% Mortality	
		48 h	72 h
		1 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(O)Cl ₂	40
	60	75	83
2 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(S)Cl ₂	40	75	85
	60	78	88
3 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(O)Cl	40	73	84
	60	80	87
4 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(S)Cl	40	75	85
	60	82	90
5 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(O)	40	86	88
	60	89	90
6 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(S)	40	88	90
	60	93	95
Malathion (standard)	40	95	97
	60	100	100

Synthesis of (C₁₄H₁₁N₂S)P(O)Cl₂ (1)/(C₁₄H₁₁N₂S)P(S)Cl₂ (2) :

In the fast stirring solution of 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole (0.001 mol) in dry THF (30 ml) and Et₃N (0.001 mol) in dry THF (20 ml), a solution of POCl₃/PSCl₃ (0.001 mol) in dry THF (30 ml) was added dropwise at 0 °C. The reaction was carried out at room temperature with continuous stirring for 20–24 h. Then it was cooled and the adduct (Et₃N.HCl) that formed during the reaction was filtered through a closed sintered funnel. The excess solvent was stripped off *in vacuo* to give a viscous solids (48% yield). A similar procedure has been applied for preparing other organophosphates derivatives. Their synthetic and analytical details are summarized in Table 6.

Conclusion

We have synthesized a series of organophosphate derivatives of 2-(4'-aminophenyl)-6-methyl benzothiazole and evaluated their antimicrobial and insecticidal activity. Their

Table 6. Physical properties and analytical data of organophosphate derivatives (1-6)

Compound	Yield (%)	State	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						Mol. wt.
			C	H	N	P	S	Cl	Found (Calcd.)
1 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(O)Cl ₂	48	Viscous solid	47.05 (47.08)	3.08 (3.10)	7.83 (7.84)	8.65 (8.67)	8.96 (8.98)	19.84 (19.85)	357.00 (357.20)
2 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S)P(S)Cl ₂	50	Viscous solid	45.04 (45.05)	2.94 (2.97)	7.50 (7.51)	8.29 (8.30)	17.15 (17.18)	18.97 (18.99)	373.00 (373.26)
3 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(O)Cl	42	Viscous solid	59.93 (59.94)	3.92 (3.95)	9.97 (9.99)	5.51 (5.52)	11.41 (11.43)	6.30 (6.32)	560.50 (561.06)
4 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₂ P(S)Cl	55	Viscous solid	58.24 (58.27)	3.81 (3.84)	9.70 (9.71)	5.36 (5.37)	16.65 (16.67)	6.12 (6.14)	576.50 (577.13)
5 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(O)	52	Viscous solid	65.92 (65.95)	4.31 (4.35)	10.97 (10.99)	4.03 (4.05)	12.56 (12.58)	-	764.00 (764.93)
6 (C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₂ S) ₃ P(S)	48	Viscous solid	64.59 (64.60)	4.23 (4.26)	10.75 (10.76)	3.94 (3.97)	16.41 (16.42)	-	780.00 (780.99)

structures have been established on the basis of spectral studies. The ³¹P NMR spectral study of organophosphate derivatives, reveals tetra coordination around the central phosphorus atom. In antimicrobial screening, it has been observed that antifungal and antibacterial activities of organophosphate derivatives increase with an increase in concentration. Results of insecticidal activity of organophosphates derivatives having P=S bond resulted in higher toxicity than having P=O bond with the same substituents attached to the phosphorus.

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